

Quantum Harmonies: An Artistic Exploration of Geiger Counter Measurements and Simulated Quantum Circuitry

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Abstract. “Quantum harmonies” is an art project that intertwines Geiger counter measurements with a simulated quantum computing circuit, translating emerging dynamics into a captivating musical experience.

Following an approach, where the most meaningful relationships between the concepts are tried to be established, the project explores the notions of superposition, entanglement, measurement, and effects of radiation.

Drawing inspiration from the many-worlds interpretation of quantum mechanics, the life of a hypothetical musical quantum organism whose sole sensory organ is a Geiger counter was modelled. Characteristic events during its journey are portrayed visually and audibly, aiming to offer an immersive way of understanding the dynamic relationship between Geiger counter measurements and quantum concepts.

1 Introduction

Although the promised advantages of quantum computing are yet to be fully realized, the advent of simulated quantum circuitry and the accessibility of cloud-based hardware are opening unprecedented opportunities for interaction and experimentation, as can be seen by the number of resources and services offered online like IBM Quantum ([1], for an introduction from a programmer’s perspective see [2]).

Despite the limitations of current quantum hardware, many useful algorithms exist already. In parallel with the exploration of quantum technology to solve mathematical problems, “the majority of quantum computer music research to date has been focused on using quantum computers to generate music algorithmically” ([3]), similar to how in the early days, “musicians started experimenting with computing far before the emergence of the vast majority of scientific, industrial and commercial computing applications in existence today” ([4], p. x).

In the realm of algorithmic composition, numerous methods for computer-generated music exist, and a wealth of resources on musical compositional styles and techniques are readily available. The programmer’s challenge lies in shaping the algorithm’s input to craft a meaningful musical expression, rather than simply accepting the computer’s output as-is.

On that notion, this paper explores the relationship of aspects of quantum mechanics in regards to algorithmic composition, if the input to the system were Geiger counter measurements.

As will be shown in this paper, this perspective offers meaningful relationships between the information that the measurements carry, and quantum circuit properties like superposition, entanglement, and measurement. In turn, with the help of a novel quantum instrument, Q1Synth [3], equally meaningful translations to expressions in music were found.

With respect to how musical composition takes place in a composer’s mind, based on the implication-realization model of melodic expectation [5], we modelled an imaginary quantum organism as it perceives different information during its lifetime, with the ability to make decisions over compositional pathways. A meaningful connection to the many-worlds interpretation of quantum mechanics is established and translated into a musical journey.

Following this section, the different concepts in place are introduced in section 2. With the knowledge about the concepts, the approach to finding meaningful relationships between them is laid out in section 3. The implementation of the overall system is described in section 4, together with explanations of the musical implications. The paper finishes with a conclusive statement in section 5, also highlighting limitations that serve as an outlook towards possible expansions of the model.

2 Concepts

In this section, concepts used in the project, such as random number generators (RNG), Geiger counter measurements, and a specific set of basic concepts regarding musical perception, style and technique - those that were evaluated to be most feasible for the use in the project - are quickly introduced.

2.1 RNG in Quantum Computing

Figure 1: A quantum circuit RNG. Generated using Qiskit (see [6])

Considering the specific circuit in figure 1, when we talk about randomness, we talk about the state of superposition, which takes place after the Hadamard gate and

until collapsed through the measurement. In this project, the truly random behaviour of the qubit's state vector position during superposition is artistically explored with the help of Geiger counter measurements, which themselves occur randomly over time.

2.2 True RNG through geiger counter measurements

Measuring background radioactivity is a popular and achievable way to generate truly random numbers. When a *Geiger-Müller tube* (see 5) is exposed to ionizing radiation, it ionizes the gas inside, resulting in a discharge of the tube and therefore a pulse. Because one can not (without extensive equipment) estimate the time at which the pulse occurs, this is under all normal circumstances considered a truly random event, which can be translated into a number by measuring the moment of occurrence in time (timestamp).

2.3 Measuring radioactivity with a Geiger-Müller tube

Because the distinct pulses need to be collected over time, the typical unit displayed on a Geiger counter is *microsieverts per hour* ($\frac{\mu\text{Sv}}{\text{h}}$). While giving a real-time means of detecting radioactivity, only after a significant amount of time, the value can be regarded as confident.

The calculation of the sievert value also depends on the sensitivity and corresponding conversion factor (*CV*) of the specific Geiger-Müller tube used. The formula states as follows:

$$\frac{\mu\text{Sv}}{\text{h}} = \text{CPM} * \text{CV}$$

For the specific tube used in this project, the soviet *SBM-20* Geiger-Müller tube, the calculation of the proper *CV* has been elaborated upon (see [7]) and concluded to be 0.00812.

Because a pulse always has the same magnitude, with this hardware we are not able to differentiate between different types of radiation. The *SBM-20* is only sensitive to beta and gamma, but not alpha radiation.

2.4 Half-Life in radioactive decay

All radioactive materials undergo a natural process called decay. According to quantum theory, it's impossible to predict exactly when a particular atom will decay, no matter how old it is. However, for a large group of identical atoms, we can measure the time it takes for half of them to decay, is called *half-life*.

This means that after the "first" half-life of a specific radioactive mass, it will take an equal amount of time for the mass to reduce to half again. The formula for the exponential decay of a specified radioactive mass is as follows, with t_{half} as half-life, M the current amount of mass, and M_0 the initial amount of mass:

$$M(t) = \frac{M_0}{2} \frac{t}{t_{\text{half}}}$$

The specific half-life values for different radioactive materials are well-known. For example, the half-life of the beta-radiating tritium, a material popularly used for perpetually-glowing illuminated wristwatches (banned for use in some countries), is $t_{\text{half, tritium}} = 12.32$ years.

2.5 The Implication-Realization model of melodic expectation

Figure 2: An implication I and realization R combined in a schema A. Source: [8] (p. 374)

First introduced by Eugene Narmour in [9], and elaborated upon in other works (most relevantly in [5]), the application of schema theory to music presents a fascinating concept of which a few core mechanics are used in the context of this project:

- During the experience of listening to a musical piece, an *implication* (denoted as I) represents a distinct segment of the music that evokes a particular association or meaning in the listener at the present moment.
- Subsequently, the specific realization of that implication, denoted as *R*, refers to the subsequent part of the musical piece — the changing musical scenery that the listener encounters after the implication part.
- The combination of implication I and realization R forms what is called a *schema*. In psychological terms, a schema represents the concept of how humans perceive information through their senses and attribute meaning to it. In the context of music, a schema A can be seen as an "expectation" that the realization R, such as an upcoming musical event, will follow if the implication I, or prior musical information, occurs.

Figure 2 depicts a schema.

An Implication can also have multiple realizations (see figure 3). To give an example of a popular implication and realization in the realm of classical music: the build-up of tension (I), that is either followed by more tension (R1) or a resolution in the music (R2). This is also an example of how a later realization can influence the attribution of the meaning of a prior part of a musical piece.

2.6 A composers' skill: Il Filo

Referring to a quote from Mozart in a letter dated August 13, 1778, he describes features of a good maestro: "good

Figure 3: An implication I can be followed by multiple realizations R_1 , R_2 , R_3 which in combination are considered separate schemata A, B, C. Source: [8] (p. 374)

Figure 4: Different pathways M, N, O, P, that a composer might take. Source: [8] (p. 378)

technical composition and the arrangement of material: *il filo*". Here, the term *il filo* (the thread), as elaborated upon in [8] (p. 369-398), accurately signifies the decisions a composer might make to shape the *path* of a composition (see figure 4). A composer could choose to adhere strictly to existing pre-defined compositional rules, when for example composing a sonata, resulting in a piece with an unadventurous and uninspired path. Conversely, a skilled composer may skillfully spin the thread, creating a path that explores lesser-known musical avenues to offer profound new insights.

3 Approach

In this section, the approaches behind the final choices taken, in search of a most meaningful relation between the introduced concepts, are elaborated upon. The choices themselves define the model of our imaginary musical quantum organism for later implementation.

3.1 Superposition of a qubit and Geiger counter pulses

While the position of the state vector of a qubit in superposition cannot be known in between measurements, the question is how logical or meaningful it would be to make any assumptions about the behaviour in superposition other than that.

What we assume however is the position of the

state vector to be in a distinct position at the exact point of measurement, from which it collapses to one of the poles.

One approach for using the input pulses could have been to initiate truly random measurements, but this was considered infeasible and subsequently rejected because it counterfeits the generation of meaningful information as it does not matter if we take the measurement (for our quantum RNG circuit) delayed or not. A measurement at a random point in time would have the same result, as a measurement at any point in time.

Therefore another meaning needs to be given to the *time of arrival of a pulse*. With the unsolved question of how a qubit "behaves" in superposition still in mind, it became evident that one assumption (although not scientifically accurate) about its state vector position could be made without completely disregarding the qubit's nature: its position could be considered truly random. By adopting this consideration, it becomes apparent that the truly random nature of Geiger counter pulses could represent the random positions occupied by a qubit's state vector at the time of pulse arrival.

The following decision was made based on this understanding:

- ▶ The true random occurrence of a pulse in time relates to the true random position of a qubit's state vector in superposition at that moment.

It could also be argued that this resembles a kind of measurement that does not lead to a collapse, but takes a snapshot of the position of the state vector as it is "behaving" in an unknown fashion.

3.2 Relating Geiger counter measurement methodology with the I-R model of melodic expectation

As introduced, a Geiger counter needs to accumulate a number of pulses over a certain period of time to be able to tell the average value of intensity with confidence. Similarly, we can envision an imaginary organism that aims to compose a musical piece by setting a sound to perceived life experiences or implications. By accumulating experiences over time, the organism forms a stable understanding of the information received, completing a schema. The realization of the implications can be directly represented by the $\frac{\mu S_V}{h}$ -value.

Because this offers a meaningful way to relate the stabilizing values of a Geiger counter measurement over time, and the stabilizing understanding a (human) organism strives for when perceiving information, the following decisions were made:

- ▶ Pulses represent distinct information in the life of the organism, as well as a new position of the state vector in superposition.
- ▶ As pulses accumulate over time, the organism forms a stable opinion about the impressions through gathered experiences during a current so-called *episode*.

- ▶ When a confidence threshold about the similarity of impressions within an episode is reached, a realization as in the I-R model occurs, completing a schema. Conversely, the point in time at which the $\frac{\mu^{SV}}{h}$ -value no longer significantly changes marks the end of an episode.
- ▶ A new schema is chained to a previous schema in the I-R model, meaning a new episode or new information - and therefore an additional qubit is to be taken into consideration for the model's circuit.
- ▶ With an episode's end representing the arrival at a conclusion, the state vector should not change anymore. A meaningful effect of the end of an episode could be a *measurement*, relating to the arrival at a confident value by the Geiger counter, and to the collapse to a distinct state also in terms of completing an I-R model schema that prior to the realization would have been indistinct.

For example, if the organism is exposed to normal background radiation, pulses arrive at different timestamps. With the duration of time in between the timestamps, the organism would accumulate the *durations* of each pulse. Based on the group it is forming within an episode and the similarity between the pulses, at a certain point, the organism would be able to predict with certain confidence how many pulses are going to arrive for the current episode. In other words, the organism is fed with environmental pieces of information, its task is to set a sound to it. It forms an opinion about the nature of the environment and as soon as it is confident enough, it considers the episode as over, symbolized by the measurement of the qubit. The following information is expected to belong to a new episode.

3.3 Relating compositional pathways with qubit entanglement

In the same way as a human composer has its own reasons to consider taking one over another pathway based on experiences made in life, our organism might want to decide if it wants to make one over another decision.

A meaningful mechanism for that could be qubit entanglement so that one episode could influence the outcome of another.

To provide the organism with a straightforward mechanism for making compositional decisions, the following choice was made:

- ▶ Drawing parallels to the way a composer makes the choice of one path over another and relations that occur between schemata, it could be made use of concepts of entanglement.

3.4 Relating harmonics to the definition of the available paths

Similarly to how a classical composer might implement different realizations in a musical piece, deciding out of a limited range of *suiting* paths, we do not want to leave

the control over the possible paths open to whatever the computer outputs without meaning. For the possible paths and therefore musical expressions that are possible by incorporating parameters of a qubit, different ideas come to mind.

By mapping the distinct collapsed states of a qubit to musical notes, it was found that with the appropriate simulated quantum circuit, a chord builds itself over time. To not overwhelm the profound basic expression that the build-up of a harmonic cord bears, the following decisions were made:

- ▶ The available basic states that a qubit can collapse towards, are represented by notes on a musical scale.
- ▶ The sounds that qubits can make together are *harmonies*. To form a harmonic chord with the note of a previous qubit, a choice is to be made among possible harmonics.
- ▶ The same way in which a composer would potentially build up a harmony one note after another, based on one base note, the qubits could produce a sound one after another that depends on previous notes.

The possible paths that are open for the organism to take at a point in time, can also be interpreted in terms of the many-worlds interpretation, in which the universe is regarded as a tree that branches over time, with the branches representing possible realisations of quantum outcomes.

3.5 Relating to half-life

Because taking measurements of radiation not only gives the organism information about the radiation values but also contaminates it, a proper way to reflect that the organism accumulated a specific amount of radiation during an episode would be to make the sound for that episode fade away for a specific duration that reflects the absorbed amount.

Therefore the following decision was made:

- ▶ The pulses accumulated during an episode could be regarded - in terms of radioactive decay - as a mass of a pre-defined material like tritium. Characteristics of an episode's decay or echo could mirror the behaviour of physical exponential decay.

3.6 Sonification of the quantum circuit using Q1Synth

Q1Synth is a novel musical instrument, introduced to the public at the beginning of the year (see [3]). It offers an audible representation of the position of a qubit's state vector on a Bloch sphere, the ability to take measurements, as well as several options for modifying the characteristics of the sound such as frequency boundaries based on a musical scale.

It allows for a straightforward application of the model as introduced to this point:

- ▶ A single qubit can be represented by a single instance of Q1Synth.
- ▶ Using the “rotate”-feature, the instrument can produce a sound continuously, based on the position of a qubit in superposition.
- ▶ The parameters of upper and lower frequency limits, of which one of is also exactly produced when measured, can be used to implement harmonics.
- ▶ Entanglement between multiple instances of Q1Synth needs to be established externally, as it is not featured.

4 Implementation

With the exact implementation of the project being made available as source code via [10], in this section the implementation is described as plain language.

4.1 Hardware

The hardware used in this project consists of:

- an ESP32.
- a self-soldered MightyOhm Geiger counter kit including an SBM-20 Geiger-Müller tube (refer to [11]), shown together in figure 5.
- a wireless network with a deployed MQTT broker, as pulses are delivered via MQTT messages.
- a capable modern desktop computer running Windows 11.

4.1.1 Connecting the ESP32 with the Geiger counter

I aimed to ensure precise measurement of the exact timestamps of arriving pulses without losing any data or introducing delays caused by other applications occupying the processing unit. To achieve this, I utilized a readily available ESP32 and its pulse counter module (refer to [12]). That way, any time a pulse is registered at the pin routed to the module, an interrupt is triggered, and a measurement can be synchronously taken (as opposed to needing to poll the data at fixed time intervals).

Figure 5: The hardware setup

An additional benefit of using this combination is that the Geiger counter can be completely powered by the ESP32’s power outlet, as it requires only 3.3 volts.

4.2 Software

While the system was developed and tested using a desktop computer running Windows 11, it is worth mentioning that the system was developed using cross-platform capable components.

4.2.1 Communication between the ESP32 and the desktop computer

As the ESP is interrupted by a pulse, the timestamp in nanoseconds is added to a list. At intervals of 1 millisecond, it is checked if the list contains any value, accounting for the fact that multiple pulses could occur at high radiation levels within 1 millisecond. If the list contains one or more values, it is sent to the wireless network that the ESP32 is connected to, using the (real-time capable) MQTT protocol ([13]).

4.2.2 Q1Synth

As introduced, Q1Synth is a musical instrument and offered as a web-browser-based musical instrument (see([14]), that can be fully controlled via the MIDI protocol.

Figure 6: The user interface of Q1Synth

Figure 6 shows the user interface of Q1Synth. Regarding the scope of this project, the parameters considered relevant for the implementation are:

- The inclination on the θ axis, which directly correlates to the position in between the poles $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. As for each pole an upper and lower limit is defined for a group of parameters - for θ , those parameters are the values for note, octave, and gain. For example, if the upper-frequency limit was set to 440Hz and the lower frequency limit to 880Hz, the frequency of the produced sound would “swing” in between the range of a full octave, a lower and an upper C, depending on the inclination on θ .
- For ϕ and λ , other parameters of the sound are influenced, like the amplitude of a separately configurable modulation envelope for the ϕ -inclination. *Most of them are unused in this project.*
- Another parameter we however do control is the “reverb” and “delay” of a qubit’s completed episode to represent half-life. To control the parameter for the qubit in general, we set both the upper and lower boundary to the same value.

- In this project, all other parameters are set to fixed, sensible values of artistic choice, which in this first implementation was to create a mostly “pure” sound, for which the effect of the deliberately influenced parameters can be distinctly made out without noise from parameters for which no meaningful relationship to the concepts was found so far.

For a handy visualisation of multiple qubits, multiple Q1Synth instances were organized utilizing the tiling feature of the Vivaldi browser ([15]). See figure 7.

Figure 7: 4 separate Q1Synth instances organized through the tiling feature of the Vivaldi browser ([15])

The MIDI input device for each Q1Synth can be set individually so that all four instances can be individually controlled.

For the sake of presentability, simplicity and regarding creating harmonic chords of limited complexity, but ultimately as an artistic choice, 4 instances of Q1Synth will be used to implement the model. It needs to be mentioned that the model can be extended to more than 4 qubits.

4.2.3 Controlling the qubits and implementing the model

The model is implemented in Python, using the python-rtmidi library ([16]).

Each Q1Synth now needs to represent a qubit, “experiencing” an episode, therefore 4 virtual midi loopback devices were created using the windows-only tool loopMIDI ([17]). Equivalent alternatives exist for Mac and Linux.

Each truly random timestamp of a pulse is translated to the MIDI-values which stand for inclination values of the axes. Since those values are 7 bits long, the 32 bits of the nanosecond timestamp can be mapped directly, by shifting the timestamp’s bits into groups of 7 (one for each axis).

A measurement takes place as soon as confidence about the probability of pulses occurring within that episode is established. For that, the μSv -value is estimated each time a pulse arrives, and collected in a list within the episode. A different μSv -value results for each pulse. By

calculating the difference between all μSv -values within an episode and building the average, this *average confidence* (AC) value decreases over time, converging to an ever-smaller number. As the value goes below a certain threshold, the *confidence level* (CL), the organism deems the episode complete, as through its aggregated experience, it deems itself confident enough to predict to a certain degree the properties of future pulses for the episode, if it would continue.

This results in a varying time period for the value to converge below the threshold in each individual episode, similar to how a unique experience takes a different time for an organism to be able to “feel” confident about “classifying” it. If very similar pulses occur at the beginning of an episode, it can be quickly deemed complete. If by chance the variance of pulses is high, or if exposed to an environment where the radiation levels suddenly increase, it is also possible for an episode to take a long amount of time, until the amount of pulses is so large that the AC converges below the CL.

Anytime the AC goes beyond the CL, the qubit is measured and it is proceeded with the next qubit. As a preventive mechanism, the CL starts at 0.05 resembling the common significance level in statistics, but is increased by 0.01 after each 10 pulses.

For determining the frequencies of a qubit, a property of the pulse is introduced named *duration* - the length of “silence” since the last pulse.

In the model, at this stage, the organism is accumulating information and trying to build an opinion about the current episode. Because an all-time lowest or shortest duration within an episode characterizes the episode most significantly in terms of impressions made and in regard to the AC value - ultimately as an artistic choice - only if a pulse has the new shortest or new longest duration within the episode, then the lower or upper frequency limit is adjusted.

All durations are saved in a *duration memory* (also those that occurred outside the episode). It is mapped at all times to the full musical scale, the highest and lowest values in the list represent the highest and lowest notes. This allows for the organism to have a memory of all durations it ever encountered, enabling it to map a duration to a frequency on the musical scale, based on the duration’s relative position in the overall duration memory.

This makes it possible for the system, if it for example only ever encountered pulses of mostly “long durations” like with background radiation, to not know about the existence of shorter durations. It will play sounds for the durations it knows within the full musical scale possible with Q1Synth. If it happens to be exposed to an environment with significantly higher radiation, its memory is expanded by the knowledge of even shorter possible durations. It would now consider the previously shortest duration to correspond to a note of lower frequency, as opposed to the earlier interpretation of it representing the highest

Figure 8: The (pseudo-) quantum circuit that is sonified stepwise within in the model

frequency. This effect weakens over time. Assuming it would stay in that changed situation for a longer amount of time, the accumulation of more and more similar durations within the overall duration memory would lead to the full musical scale being covered more and more again. This represents the ability of adaptation for an organism in an initially unfamiliar environment.

Because of the limitation of 4 Qubits, they were grouped into a larger *meta-episode* consisting of 4 single episodes. This meta-episode represents the composition of a harmony of 4 notes, by 4 compositional episodes in which experiences were processed.

To create a meaningful compositional pathway, the possible frequencies that together create a harmonic chord - the chord factors - are to be defined. No meaningful relationship was found for that definition, and it was deemed to be left open to artistic choice. Through experimentation, it was found that alternating factors of thirds and fifths offer a great variety of approachable harmonics for the model to explore generatively. In this implementation, the first found frequencies are considered the base notes for the grid on which the next found frequencies need to match. Whenever the upper or lower frequency of a qubit is set, a match on that grid is ensured, and a chord is built as of the predefined rules. If it already exists within the list of other frequencies, or if it would not result in harmony, the next best-fitting place is searched iteratively, until each frequency has its own place in the chord.

This enforces the generation of a tetrad at the end of a meta-episode, but leaves it open to the model, to create unexpected harmonies also for similar situations, that still might share similar characteristics.

As the organism in our case perceives information sequentially and builds a chord sequentially, the artistic decision was made to also sequentially “activate” qubits as their episode starts, and for them to remain playing from activation throughout the meta-episode - similarly to how accompanying notes to a chord would be playing simultaneously.

As described in the approach, at the end of a single episode, the qubit is being measured, with the conclusion of two boundaries set and the collapse into one over the other. This signifies that the previous information

is not altered anymore, the state vector of the episode does not change anymore with each pulse.

As a way to incorporate an artistically suiting but - in the fields of quantum computing - not very interesting form of entanglement, or rather correlation, this implementation makes use of the concept of a CNOT gate. Each qubit within a meta-episode is the target of a CNOT gate to its successor being the control qubit. Although this correlation can be explained classically, it provides an audible and visual artistic representation of a form of correlation between qubits.

This gives the imaginary organism a way of retrospectively changing a decision based on new experiences made and a way to tell if a relationship between them exists or not. No entanglement takes place in between meta-episodes.

For a graphical representation that depicts the “workflow” implemented in this model, in the form of a (pseudo-) quantum circuit, see figure 8.

At the end of a meta-episode, a reset was implemented by assigning the default values to variables that are not important for the “long-term” memory, making it possible for a new meta-episode to start.

For a representation of half-life, the values of the reverb and delay are set for each episode, according to the accumulated count of pulses. The count is compared at all times to a memory of counts of prior finished episodes and matched to the scale of reverb and delay - again relative to its position in the memory of all counts. An all-time highest count would result in the longest delay and reverb for an episode, for it would represent more amount of accumulated mass in terms of exponential decay.

The complete audible process from the listener’s perspective is to be regarded as *the composition*.

5 Conclusion

A meaningful approach has been discovered to attribute significance to the input Geiger counter pulses and interweave them with concepts of quantum computing, forming a connection to an imaginary quantum organism that outputs a musical composition related to processes of a composer’s mind. This connection enables an approachable

sonification of the concepts and their effects.

Notably, the modelled organism exhibits properties akin to a human composer with memory. As the organism encounters diverse experiences throughout its lifetime, it accumulates knowledge about its environment. Consequently, depending on the context in which it resides, the organism interprets new information and groups episodes of its life into unique “memories” (measurements), each time in a different way than it would have before.

A compositional technique, that consists of the artistic simulation of a specific (pseudo-) quantum circuit through which is progressed stepwise, and where each event is sonified, is presented. To an extent, the notion of entanglement is incorporated, although in reality it is a simple correlation that can be explained classically: successor qubits influence previous already measured qubits through a CNOT gate. This reflects a choice a composer could make of one pathway over another, drawing parallels to the many-worlds interpretation of quantum mechanics.

The substantial variance in geiger counter pulses, and the very high precision of measured timestamps achieved through an interrupt-based implementation, allow for a broad spectrum of musical pathways to be explored, even more so if more dramatic changes occur in the environment. The influence of the information the organism experiences during its lifetime is reflected in a characteristic repeated build-up of a harmonic chord, played by four sonified qubits — “quantum harmonies”.

5.1 Limitations and outlook

- In this study, we utilize true RNGs in the domain of music composition. This exploration also aims to shed light on potential ways of incorporating true randomness into the creative process. Nevertheless, the impact of using truly random numbers, as made accessible via quantum hardware, compared to traditional pseudo-randomized input, for this or other generative models, could be a matter of investigation.
- A mechanism for highlighting the difference between true and pseudo-randomized input values could be implemented. This mechanism would test the input for true statistical randomness and adjust the instrument’s parameters in a meaningful way. Such an implementation would maybe even offer a means of error/deviation for the investigation mentioned before - even if that investigation was to determine that the impact of true randomness is minimal or non-existent, it would offer a means of sonifying true randomness as accessible via quantum hardware.
- For now, rhythm is not taken into consideration, while it could be achieved by mapping the notes onto the quantized grid of a sequencer, making it possible to for example repeat the notes based on the duration of the episode.
- The possibilities for the sound that a measured qubit can produce are right now distinct notes.

This could be changed, for example, to a sequence of notes from a repertoire of a certain musical style, to offer for more complex compositions to take place.

- Here, 4 qubits were taken into consideration, to form a tetrad. As mentioned, this amount of qubits is theoretically not limited, and practically in this project only by the amount of possible midi channels and ways of representation. With more qubits, and other compositional ideas in mind than a tetrad, the idea of the model to step through the events of a quantum circuit sequentially while sonifying the events through Q1Synth could be made use of in other projects.
- Other parameters of Q1Synth could be used to for example make a more noisy sound for an episode that contains more variance in radiation.
- For now only the parameters reverb and delay are controlled to represent half-life, not accurately portraying exponential decay, as the slope of modulation cannot be controlled. The actual behavior of exponential decay could be implemented by introducing an additional recording and playback instrument into the chain, that records the sound at the time at which they occur, to repeat them and decay the volume of each repetition to resemble the decay of half-lives of an accumulated radioactive mass.

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